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Impact Of Armed Banditry On Socio Economic Development In Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study examined the impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria. The study used a survey research design. The target population of the study comprised of the entire tertiary institution students in the North-West and North-Central geo-political zones of the country. The study used simple random sampling technique in selecting the respondents. A total number of 160 male and 221 female higher institution students were selected from 8 purposively selected schools to participate in the study. The study used a questionnaire titled “Impact of Armed Banditry on Socio-Economic Development in Nigeria (IABSEDN)”. The instrument was prepared based on the modified Likert-scale of Strongly Agree (SD), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was validated and the reliability was establish at 0.82 using the split half reliability method determined through the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficiency formula. The finding reveals that gender does not make a difference in the opinion of students regarding the causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria. It was recommended that government should intensify efforts to mobilize financial and human resources to fund disarmament, and de-radicalization programmes to curtail the problems of arms proliferation across the country.

Keywords: armed banditry, arms proliferation, development

INTRODUCTION

The majority of businesses in the northern Nigeria have shut down due to security concerns brought on by armed bandits. There has been an increase in youth unemployment and illiteracy, and people’s living situations have worsened. Worldwide, ongoing violent crises and conflicts have disrupted the peaceful existence of nations in recent times. These crises and conflicts manifest as protests, uprisings, and organized crimes like banditry and kidnapping (Ahmed, 2023).

Banditry is the act of raiding and attacking victims by armed groups, using offensive or defensive weapons, either premeditated or not (Yusuf and Bamidele, 2022). As a result of the intense attacks, the socio-economic activities in the northern region have experienced a significant decline. Agricultural productivity have been severally affected, as farmers are reluctant to go to their farms due to the insecurity. Tajudeen (2023) observed that the emergence of criminal bandits in the northern part of the

country has further deteriorated the socio-economic growth of the country already crippled by Boko Haram insurgency and other security challenges.

Armed banditry has been a major security challenge confronting Nigeria in recent years. Attacks orchestrated by these armed bandits have continued to escalate with attendant consequences of loss of human lives, destruction of property, displacement of persons, loss of livelihoods and disruption of socio-economic activities. Bello and Ahmed (2022) stressed that banditry is the taking of property using force or the threat of force, often by a group, usually made up of men. They usually operate in the shadows, often on the outskirts of civilization, in remote locations, and it is done out of necessity. This indicates that banditry is a criminal activity characterized by kidnapping, armed robberies, cattle thefts and village raids. It is important to remember that these bandits are not complete strangers, as some of them are known to be members of the community who have been victims of suffering and injuries as a result of their actions. Reports indicate the flourishing of bandit groups, whose members are seen displaying automatic weapons, terrorizing herders' settlements, farms, villages and the highways with the mission of killing people, kidnapping and pillaging cows (Tirimisiyu, 2020). It was reported that between 2015 and 2020, more than 48,000 cattle were rustled from commercial livestock farms and traditional herders in Northern Nigeria while about 247 attacks were made by bandits and 2,347 deaths were recorded between January and December, 2023. In most cases, the bandits killed and maimed the people and raped the women before dispossessing them of their cows while in some instances, they also kidnapped girls or women in the process (Ayomide, 2022).

Banditry is a heinous crime posing a great security challenge to the Northern part of Nigeria. Security challenges continue to significantly hinder meaningful development in Nigeria. Insecurity not only threatens the lives and properties of citizens but also deters local businesses, scares away foreign investment, and tarnishes the state's image. As an agriculturally dominant country, any disruption that displaces farmers from their lands and deprives them of their livelihood spells trouble for the economy. Ayetoro (2021) opined that this is already evident in the current food shortages and high cost of living which contribute to Nigeria's poor human development indicators, making it one of the poorest producers of foodstuffs that will sustain the livelihood of the citizens. The threat of armed banditry has recently become a recurring menace to the peace and survival of the people as it affects community services, healthcare, education, local markets, livestock rearing, gold mining, agricultural produce that are vital factors in explaining the culture and values of people in the area, have been truncated by the activities of armed bandits.

It should be noted that a weak security system complements the alarming rate of banditry in Nigeria. This could have possibly been caused by the inadequate equipment for the security arm of government, both in weaponry and training (Tresure, 2012). Also, poor attitudinal and behavioural disposition of security personnel is something else. Security personnel assigned to deal with given security situations lack the expertise and equipment to handle the situations in a way to prevent them from occurring. Instead of many of them being national watch dogs and defending national interest and values, and protecting people from being harmed by criminals, they become saboteurs of government efforts, by supporting and fuelling insecurity through either leaking vital security information or conniving with criminals to acquire weapons or to escape the long arm of the law (Lawal and Abdulahi, 2022).

Furthermore, there has been an incremental influx of small arms and light weapons (SALWs) into Nigeria from Sahel since the fall of Ghadafi's regime in Libya (Peters, 2016). These arms and weapons end up in the hands of non-state actors like terrorists, bandits, militants, who use them to terrorize individuals and communities. Coupled with it is the issue of poverty as well as poor governance which contributed significantly to the rising wave of banditry in Nigeria. The failure of successive administrations in Nigeria to address the challenges of poverty bedeviling the nation has made life burdensome and only the fittest survive. As Nigeria is re-strategizing on ways to control the menace of armed banditry, insurgency and corruption having suffered from Boko Haram insurgency which has crippled its socio-economic development, new emerging security threats are fast paving their way to either complement or to gradually replace earlier threats to the country's socio-economic development.

The activities on banditry over the years have paralyzed economic activities in Nigeria since majority of the populace derived their livelihood from farming. The menace posed by banditry has affected rural populace income livelihood thereby making them sojourning in the neighbouring local government area. Nigeria is facing series of challenges which are affecting the economic growth of the country. One of such problems bedeviling economic growth of the country is the issue of kidnapping and banditry (Olaajo & Awoniyi, 2022). This has turned into a social problem which is affecting virtually every member of the Nigerian society in one way or the other. Banditry and other forms of conflicts have recently come to constitute a subject of great concern in Nigeria. Study and other media report indicate that, in the first quarter of 2014 alone, 262 persons lost their lives in 15 separate attacks in Benue state and before and after the 2019 general election sporadic clashes has continued. In one instance, bandits brazenly attacked the state governors convey. Similarly, 16 separate attacks were reported in Plateau and Kaduna state. Banditry activities have of recent increased tremendously along Abuja-Kaduna road, the development left many motorist and passengers unaccounted for just as their belongings were carted away by the bandits (Chukwueme and Agaba, 2019).

Banditry has emerged as the new bogeyman for insecurity in Nigeria, joining a long and still growing list that includes Boko Haram, cultists, herdsmen, militants and host of others. In different parts of the North-West, from Birnin Gwari in Kaduna to Tsafe in Zamfara, bandits are offered as the trope of an intolerable carnage, and the inexplicable haplessness Federal Government that does not appear to care for much else in an election season (Olaajo & Awoniyi, 2022). Nigeria Watch (2011) observed that banditry means occurrence of prevalence of armed robbery or violent crime. It involves the use of force, or threat to that effect, to intimidate a person with the intent to robs, rape or kill. Banditry is a crime, as well as cause violence in contemporary societies. The facts are scary. About 1,100 people were murdered in 2018 in states of Northwest, over 2,200 were killed in 2019 and 1,600 killed in 2020. According to ACAPS (2020) about 247,000 people had been displaced while their activities alone have led to the production of more than 41,000 refugees. In Zamfara alone, over 8,000 people have been murdered in the last decade, 200,000 displaced internally and others fleeing to neighbouring states. ICGP report (2020) stressed that the situation in so porous already that the religious leader and sultan of Sokoto, Muhammadu Sa ad Abubakar opined that “Bandits now move in the North from house to house with AK47 and lamented that the region had become the worst place to live in Nigeria.

The recent reported incidences of banditry in Northwest and North central geopolitical zones are presented below:

Table 1: Recent incidences of Banditry in Nigeria

S/N	Newspaper	Reporter(s)	Date of publication	Nature and Place of Attack	Causalities
1.	The Punch	Gbenro Adeoye	March 31, 2018	Bandits attacked Bawan Daji village of Anka LGA of Zamfara state and killed over 30 peoples	Over 30 people were killed
2.	The Nation	The Nation	March 1, 2019	21 killed in Kawaye village in Bagega community of Anka LGA of Zamfara State.	21 people were killed and 40 others abducted
3.	The Punch	The Punch	June 9, 2019	25 killed in bandit attacks in Klahu, Tsage and Geeri villages in Rabah LGA of Sokoto State.	25 people were killed
4.	The Punch	Olaide Oyelude	July 19, 2019	11 killed in bandit attacks on Kandara and Danmusa LGA of Sokoto State.	11 people were killed.
5.	The Nation	The Nation	August 19,	Four villagers were killed in	Death of 4

			2019	banditry attacks in Tsayu village of Jibiya LGA of Katsnia State.	villagers
6.	The Punch	Maiharaji Altine	January 17, 2020	Zamfara bandit kill 31 persons in attacks in Tsayu village in Gummi LGA and Makosa village in Zurmi LGA of Zamfara State.	Death of 31 persons
7.	Nigerian Tribune	Muhammad Sabiu	March 2, 2020	Bandits kill 50 people in villages in Igabi and Giwa LGA of Kaduna State.	50 people were killed while several others injured
8.	The Punch	Olaide Oyelude	April 20, 2020	Bandits kill 47 people in multiple attacks on Kurechin Dutse, Makauwachi and Daule villages in Katsina State.	A total of 47 people were killed in all the villages
9.	The Nation	AbdulGafar Alabelewe	April 24, 2020	Bandits kill seven and kidnap one in Akwunakwo, Kabriasha and Damba villages in Chikun LGA of Kaduna State.	7 persons were killed and 1 person was kidnapped
10.	Nigerian Tribune	Muhammad Sabiu	May 6, 2020	5 killed, DPO shot and 1 kidnap in multiple bandit attack at Faskari and Sabuwa LGA of Katsina State.	5 people were killed, 1 kidnapped and DPO was shot
11.	The Punch	Maiharaji Altine	May 20, 2020	Bandits kill 12 in attack on three (3) communities in Tsafe LGA of Zamfara State	Death of 12 people and cart away animals
12.	The Punch	Maiharaji Altine	June 5, 2020	Bandits kill 21 people in Maru and Talata-Mafara LGA of Zamfara state	Death of 21 people
13.	The Nation	Justina Asishana	June 25, 2020	Four fered killed in Sunko, Gavya and Marafa communities in Manta District of Shiroro LGA of Niger State.	Death of 4 persons
14.	The Nation	Justina Asishana	July 21, 2020	16 persons kidnapped in bandit attacks in Magari and Tungan-Bajo communities of Rafi LGA, Niger State.	16 persons were kidnapped
15.	The Nation	AbdulGafar Alabelewe	July 26,2020	Bandits kill 10 in two attacks on 3 villages of Jema's and Kaura LGA of Kaduna State.	10 persons were killed
16.	The Punch	Olaide Oyelude	August 9, 2020	Eight bandits, two others skilled after bandits attacks on Zamfara village in Batsari LGA of Katsina State.	Death of 2 villagers and 8 bandits
17.	Vanguard	Vanguard	Sept. 4, 2020	Bandits kill 22 people, including 19 vigilantes in	22 people were killed

				Dukku and Kagara towns, Niger State.	
18.	Vanguard	Ibrahim Hassan Wugo	Sept. 13, 2020	Bandits abduct 16 family members of Udawa farming communities of Kaduna State.	16 people were killed
19.	Vanguard	Ibrahim Hassan Wugo	Sept. 18, 2020	Bandits invade police station in Tangaza LGA of Sokoto State.	DPO and 1 inspector were killed and 2 women abducted
20.	Vanguard	Wole Mosadomi and Shehu Danjuma	Oct. 12, 2020	Bandits kill 14 persons in Ruwan Godiya village of Faskari LGA of Kastina state and Kagara town of Fafi LGA of Niger State.	14 people were killed, 3 injured and 1 kidnapped
				Bandits kill Southern Kaduna District head and son	Death of people
21.	Vanguard	Ibrahim Hassan Wugo	Nov. 17, 2020	Bandits kidnap 8 BABU students on the Kaduna Abuja Road.	8 students were kidnapped
22.	Vanguard	Wole Mosadomi	Nov.20, 2020	Bandits Kidnap 14 And Kill Mobile Policemen In Mariya LGA Of Niger Delta State.	14 people were kidnapped and death of a policemen
23.	Vanguard	Ifeanyi Nwannah	Nov.23, 2020	Armed Bandits Kidnap Imam, 17 Worshippers From A Mosque In Kanoma District, Maru LGA Zamfara State.	18 persons were kidnapped.
24.	Vanguard	Bashir Bello	Dec. 1, 2020	Bandits Invade Tashar Bama, Dogun Muaze And Unguwar Maigayya Villages Of Sabuwa LGA Of Katsina State.	7 farmers including nursing mother were killed and abduct 30 others
25.	Vanguard	Vanguard	Dec. 5, 2020	Bandits Attack Kasuwan Magani Town In Kajuru LGA Of Kaduna State.	1 persons was killed
26.	Daily Posi	Daily post	Dec. 10, 2020	Kidnappers raid Rmahbe layout in Ushafa, Abuja	3 persons were abducted
27.	The Nation	Uja Emmanuel	Dec. 12, 2020	Gun Men Kill Four And Injure Seven In Tse-Angande In Makurdi LGA Of Benue State.	Death of 4 persons and 7 persons injured
28.	Vanguard	Vanguard	Dec. 12, 2020	Banditry: Police confirm attack on Government Science Secondary School (GSSS) in	About 333 students missed

				Kankara LGA of Katsina State.	
29.	The Nation	Justina Asishana	Dec. 13, 2020	Bandits kill ECWA Gospel Kubwa Kuta in Chukuba village of Shiroro LGA of Niger Delta	1 person was killed and 20 others were kidnapped
30.	VOA News	VOA News	Sept. 22, 2021	Bandits attack Bini primary health clinic, Sokoto	More than 100 killed
31.	Vatican News	Nathan Morley	Dec. 20, 2021	Armed Bandits Attack Kauran Fawa Markets and Rlheyia Villages In Idasu, Giwa LGA Of Kaduna State.	38 people were killed
32.	Vatican News	Nathan Morley	Oct. 19, 2021	Bandits Attack Sokoto State.	12 peoples were killed
33.	Vanguard	Ibrahim Hassan Wuyo	Dec. 23, 2021	Bandits kill 6, kidnap many travelers in Birnin Gwari Road	6 people were killed and many were kidnapped.

**Source: Nigeria Newspapers
Olaajo and Awoniyi's compilation from Nigeria's daily Newspapers (2022).**

Statement of the Problem

Security, peace, stability, and good governance are essential for any nation to achieve significant socio-economic development. It is widely believed that there is a strong correlation between adequate security and overall development. Over the past decade, security challenges have significantly hindered meaningful development in Nigeria. Banditry has become a major issue that the government is trying to manage to enhance human security and socio-economic development. Despite numerous government strategies, measures, and interventions to combat this menace, the problem persists, making it increasingly difficult for the country to mitigate it effectively. The government has introduced various policies and spent billions of naira to address banditry, yet incidents continue to occur daily in many communities within the country. The rise banditry has led to widespread insecurity and posed a threat to Nigeria's socio-economic development. It is against this background that the paper tends to investigate the analysis of impact of armed banditry on Nigeria's socio-economic development in Nigeria.

Research Questions

To give direction to the study, the following research questions were answered.

1. What are the impacts of armed banditry on Nigeria's socio-economic development between male and female tertiary institutions students?
2. What are the possible causes and effects of armed banditry on Nigeria citizens and socio-economic development among rural and urban tertiary institution students?

Hypotheses

These research hypotheses were tested in the study at 0.05 level of significant.

- Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean opinion score of male and female students on causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria among rural and urban students.
- Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean opinion score of rural and urban tertiary institution students on causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria among students.

METHODOLOGY

The study used a survey research design. It adopted because according to Akinkunmi (2020), survey research design allows data to be collected in national settings. The target population of the study comprised of the entire tertiary constitution students in the Northwest and North central geo-political zones of the country. The study used simple random sampling technique in selecting the respondents. A total number of 160 male and 221 female higher institution students were selected from 8 purposively selected schools to participate in the study. The simple percentage was used to determine the number of students to be picked from each school. The study used a questionnaire titled “Impact of Armed Banditry on Socio-Economic Development in Nigeria” (IABSEDN). The instrument was prepared based on the modified Likert-four point scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). The instrument was validated by experts in Measurement and Evaluation and Social Studies for face and content validity. The reliability was established at 0.82 using the split-half reliability method determined through the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficiency formula.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What are the impacts of armed banditry on Nigeria’s socio-economic development between male and female tertiary institutions students?*

In order to answer this research question, the mean opinion score and standard deviation of the respondents we computed. Table 1 presents the mean opinion score and standard deviation of male and female tertiary institution respondents.

Table 1: Mean Opinion Score and Standard Deviation of male and female students (respondents) on the impact of armed banditry on Nigeria’s socio-economic development.

Gender	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Males	196	65.7092	8.88803
Females	185	64.1622	9.43027
Total	381		

Table 1 illustrates that male respondents had a mean opinion score of 65.7092 with a standard deviation of 8.88803 while female respondents had a mean opinion score of 64.1622 with a standard deviation of 9.43027. This indicates that the mean opinion score of male respondents is higher than the mean opinion score of female respondents. Therefore, there is a slight difference between the mean opinion score of male students and their female counterpart regarding the impact of armed banditry on Nigeria’s socio-economic development. Armed banditry has impacted negatively on both male and female respondents in the aspect of economic development as shown in the direction of their responses.

Research Question 2: *What are the possible causes and effects of armed banditry on Nigeria citizens and socio-economic development among rural and urban tertiary institution students?*

In order to answer this research question, the mean opinion score and standard deviation of the respondents were computed. Table 2 presents the mean opinion score and standard deviation of the respondents based on their school location.

Table 2: Mean Opinion Score and Standard Deviation of Urban and Rural respondents on the possible causes and effect of armed banditry on Nigeria citizens and socio-economic development

Location	N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Urban	240	64.7125	9.55477
Rural	141	65.3759	8.50927
Total	381		

Table 2 illustrates that urban respondents had mean opinion score of 64.7125 with a standard deviation of 9.55477 while rural respondents had mean opinion score of 65.3759 with a standard deviation of 8.50927. This means that the mean opinion score of urban respondents is lower than the mean opinion score of

rural respondents. Therefore, there is a slight difference between the mean opinion score of urban tertiary institution students and that of their rural counterpart regarding the possible causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria. This means that armed banditry has impacted negatively on the Nigeria's citizens and socio-economy development as shown in the direction of their responses.

Testing of Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean opinion score of male and female tertiary institution students on the causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria among students. In order to test the hypothesis, the mean opinion score of male respondents and that of their female counterpart were subjected to t-test analysis. Table 5 presents the result of the t-test analysis for the two groups.

Table 3: Analysis of t-test of Mean Opinion Score of Male and Female Respondents

Gender	N	Mean	Std	t	df	P-value
Males	196	65.7092	8.88803	1.648	378	0.100
Females	185	64.1622	9.43027			

At 0.05 alpha level of significance

Table 3 illustrates that the $t=1.648$, $df = 379$, $p = 0.100$, which indicates that the probability value (P) is greater than the alpha level ($P>0.05$). Since the probability value is greater than the alpha level, the (H_0) null hypothesis is retained. Therefore, the researchers concludes that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion score of male and female tertiary institution students on the causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean opinion score of students on the possible causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria. In order to test the hypothesis, the mean opinion score of urban respondents and that of their rural counterpart were subjected to t-test analysis.

Table 4: Analysis of t-test of Mean Opinion Score of Urban Respondents and that of their Rural Counterpart

Location	N	Mean	Std	t	df	P-value
Urban	240	64.7125	9.55477	-681	379	0.496
Rural	141	65.3759	8.50927			

At 0.05 alpha level of significance

Table 4 shows that the $t = -681$, $df = 379$, $p = 0.496$, which indicates that the probability value (P) is greater than the alpha level ($p> 0.05$). Since the probability value is greater than the alpha level, the (H_0) null hypothesis is retained. Therefore, the researchers concludes that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion score of urban and rural tertiary institution students on the causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings of the hypothesis reveals no significant difference between the mean opinion score of male and female tertiary institution students on the causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria. The result of data analysis on hypotheses one illustrates no significant difference between the mean opinion score of male and female tertiary institution students. This finding implies that gender does not make a difference in the opinion of students regarding the causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria. This finding is online with the opinion of Ibrahim and Usman (2021) who observed that banditry causes a decline in the average per capital income of the community, undermines human dignity among women, abuse men and disrupts food security. It also revealed that, the socio-economic impact of banditry in study area has been very devastating to the people

living in those areas. Tirimisiyu (2020) stressed that the heinous act was characterized by indiscriminate attacks which resulted to kidnapping, rapping and killing of cattle owners, vigilante members, and other innocent rural dwellers by the various gangs of armed bandits. The most terrible and devastating moment of these activities was when the bandits decided to embark on reprisal killings in the affected areas. It should be noted that those involved in banditry and other violent crimes in the affected areas under study were mostly herdsmen who have a vast knowledge and skills on how to quietly move in the forest. Again, both male and female opined that the presence of insecurity in any environment constitutes threat to achieving the development as lives and properties are in danger, hinders business activities and discourages local and foreign investors, all of which stifles and retards socio-economic development of a country. Ibrahim and Usman (2021) stressed that banditry emerged because politicians in the affected states in Nigeria sponsored and armed some youth as political thugs to achieve their political ambition. These groups of youths were later abandoned after winning the election, who then went into drug abuse, into armed gangs or banditry harassing or attacking villages using motorbikes.

The result of hypothesis two reveals that there is no significant difference between the mean opinion score of urban and rural tertiary institution students on the causes and impact of armed banditry on socio-economic development in Nigeria. This finding corroborates with that of Akinkunmi (2020) who found no significant mean score of urban and rural respondents' opinion on the causes and effect of armed banditry on economic development of Zamfara State. A new style of banditry emerged which involved not only rustling the cattle but killing the owners and scaring people away from their communities. Most worrisome is that the armed banditry started at the wake of the nation's efforts to resuscitate the socio-economic problems created by the Niger Delta militants. This indeed has remained topical and constitute a serious cause of concern to government and the private sector economy of Nigeria. To the government in particular, the question of banditry has recently become a crucial issue in the Nigeria's struggle for good government, sustainable development and sustainable socio-economic development. The predominant threat and security challenges are emanating from unbaiting attacks on Nigerian citizens, individuals, public and government installations, kidnapping and destruction of properties.

CONCLUSION

The place of security in the socio-economic development in a region, community or country can never be overlooked. This study investigated the various forms of banditism and their impact on socio-economic development in Nigeria. It is argued that banditry is responsible for the deplorable state of socio-economic indices in Nigeria. The study shows that bandit activities such as cattle theft, village attacks, and kidnapping have a devastating impact on the average per capital income of the people, human dignity among women, and food security and host of others. Moreover, the results shows a statistical significant and reliably confirmed that banditry is a criminal activity that influence socio-economic conditions. Canalization and destruction of life and socio-economic activities such as education healthcare, farming, commerce trading, agricultural and livestock rearing, displacement of communities, creating widespread anxiety and tension in Nigeria. Hence, foreign workers are scare of coming to work in Nigeria which is affecting Nigeria socio-economic development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Nigeria government should strategize to create meaningful employment for the youths encapsulated in programmes which aim at addressing the endemic poverty in Nigeria.
2. There should be a special courts to try suspected cases of banditry/terrorism rather than the judicial courts which can be slow in their processes. Convicts should be summarily dealt with according to the statutes on terrorism so as to serve as deterrence to prospective terrorists.
3. There should be re-orientation to inculcate ethical values and reverence for life and human rights in the people and also the need to co-exist irrespective of religions or ethnic inclinations.

4. Nigeria government should sustain the military efforts in prosecuting the war against banditry as well as equip the security forces with both types of modern equipment and necessary incentives to enable them carry out their duties without hindrances.
5. Government should intensify efforts to mobilize financial and human resources to fund disarmament, and de-radicalization programmes o curtail the problems of arms proliferation across the region.

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